

NOx pathways in lean technically premixed swirling H2-air turbulent flame

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Abstract

Today's climate and energy challenges are pushing the use of decarbonised and renewable alternative fuels in the field of power generation and transportation. Hydrogen as a fuel is a good candidate to meet these requirements since it offers no-carbon emissions and can play the role of energy vector to store energy in excess produced by renewable energy. Nonetheless, NOx production needs to be assessed. This work deals with this problem by proposing high-fidelity LES simulations of NOx production of 100% technically premixed hydrogen-air flame. This refers to experiments performed at the Berlin Institute of Technology. With the purpose to properly solve the combustion process and the NOx production, the static mesh refinement (SMR) and the conjugate heat transfer (CHT) techniques have been applied by showing their impact on the numerical solution. To allow NOx prediction, a new reduced kinetic scheme for air-H2 combustion (15 species and 47 reactions) has been developed on purpose taking into account the NOx

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pathways. While the application of CHT does not change the global amount of NO emitted, it affects the amount of N₂O obtained at the exit of the combustion chamber. Moreover, a detailed analysis of the NO formation is presented proving that the numerical model and the reduced chemical kinetic scheme are able to predict the NO dynamic formation accounting for the primary and secondary route: N₂O and NNH.

Keywords: Hydrogen/air combustion, NO_x, Large Eddy Simulation, Reduced chemistry, Conjugate Heat Transfer

1. Introduction

Hydrogen (H₂) is nowadays considered as the most promising technical solution to reach European Union goal of zero-net CO₂ emissions by 2050, opening a new era of decarbonized combustion [1]. Nevertheless, even if H₂ does not contribute through chemical reactions to CO₂ emissions, its chain of reactions leads to the production of nitrogen oxides, mainly NO, NO₂ and N₂O. In the last decades, a lot of work has been devoted to the study of N-gases being they responsible of air pollution and global warming. Indeed, N₂O is a strong and long lifetime greenhouse gases (GHG) representing the 7% of GHG produced in Europe with an increasing rate of 2% per decade [2]. In addition, in combustion systems N₂O is a precursor of the other NO_x through reactions $\text{N}_2\text{O} + \text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{NO} + \text{NO}$ and $\text{N}_2\text{O} + \text{H} \rightleftharpoons \text{NO} + \text{NH}$ [3]. Elevated levels of NO and NO₂ are the responsible of tropospheric ozone formation and acidification of the atmosphere [4]. From this scenario, clearly appears that an intense use of hydrogen as fuel in combustion systems calls for a full understanding of the formation mechanism responsible of these

pollutants with the objective of designing novel injectors able to moderate their emissions. Developments are also required for numerical tools that must ensure accurate prediction standards, thus increasing their potential as a complement to experimental analyses. The present article deals with these challenges by proposing an high-fidelity numerical analysis of NO_x production by a turbulent lean technically premixed swirling hydrogen-air flame.

The study of NO_x production and destruction after combustion of different fuels in oxygen-nitrogen mixtures pones its basis in the last century. Herein a brief summary of the study on NO reactions, which is not intended to be exhaustive of all the literature, is proposed. Zeldovich [5] was the first to clarify the thermal character of the NO formation in combustion and explosion. Homer et al. [6] investigated the importance of oxygen atom overshoot close to the flame front and the additional HO₂ route to improve the modeling of NO at high temperature. Glarborg et al. [7] proposed a comprehensive reaction scheme for NO_x prediction based on carbon fuels studies. A large variety of experiments and new models have been carried out on hydrogen laminar flames to investigate the primary sources of NO_x production, e.g. Refs. [8], but also its secondary routes which are important when the thermal NO emissions are mitigated [9]. In the last decade of the last century, more attention has been paid to secondary routes since they actively participate in lean and low temperature combustion. For instance, Bozzelli et al. [10] proposed the NNH route for the first time also investigating its link with the N₂O pathways. Glarborg [11] recently reviewed the NO modeling state of the art highlighting the importance of N₂O and NNH routes, and showing the reasons why this topic is still a great challenge in the community. Recently,

Durocher et al. [12] demonstrated experimentally that the modern detailed kinetic mechanisms present in the literature are now able to describe with fewer uncertainties the N_2O and NNH pathways. Focusing on hydrogen, few experimental studies have been performed in gas turbines configurations for multiple injector designs in order to evaluate the impact of lean hydrogen combustion on NOx production. The impact of small hydrogen addition in the NOx levels produced by methane-air flame was at first investigated for classical Dry Low NOx systems [13]. Recently, similar studies have been also performed in the MIRADAS test rig developed at IMFT laboratory where a separate injection of small quantity of hydrogen has been proved to be able to stabilize a thermo-acoustically unstable flame with, however, a negative impact on NOx levels [14]. Technically premixed hydrogen-air flames have been also investigated in the last years by the research group of the Berlin Institute of Technology (TUB) [15] with the aim of designing injectors able to contrast flashback inclination while keeping low levels of NOx (<10 ppm NOx at 15% O_2) [15]. Similar objectives have also driven the developments of novel designs as the micro-mixing injector proposed by Tekin et al. [16].

For what concerns the numerical investigations, a variety of Direct Numerical Simulations (DNS) can be found in literature focusing on H_2 flames. Rieth et al. [17] pointed out the importance of preferential diffusion in hydrogen air flame even at $Ka \gg 1$, in which the species molecular diffusion is usually neglected. Aspden et al. [18] studied lean hydrogen combustion, $\phi=0.4$, by varying the Ka number showing how high turbulent flames decouple heat release rate and fuel consumption. DNS of turbulent swirled imposed premixed flames have been performed in the past to investigate

the structure of the recirculation zones and the mechanisms of reaction. Minamoto et al. [19] showed a correlation between reaction rates and both scalar gradient and small turbulence structures. Aoki et al. [20] investigated the impact of strain on the heat release rate at different swirl numbers. None of aforementioned works focuses on pollutants predictions. Only few DNS simulations focused on NO formation. For instance, Netzer et al. [21] analyzed the impact of hydrogen preferential diffusion and NO formation for lean-to-rich ammonia/hydrogen/nitrogen-air flames.

When it comes to complex configurations, Large Eddy Simulations (LES) have also been extensively used in the recent years providing detailed understanding of the coupling between elementary physical processes involved in the combustion of complex flames at reasonable computational cost. Focusing on hydrogen applications, most studies have been performed considering H₂ diluted with conventional fuels. Gadalla et al. [22] analyzed by LES the impact of tri-fuel (diesel-methanol-hydrogen) combustion for marine applications. For what concerns methane enrichment with hydrogen, e.g., Laera et al. [23] focused on the stabilization of CH₄ flames with H₂ injection, Agostinelli et al. [24] studied the impact of H₂-enrichment on the flame structure and combustion dynamics of a CH₄-air swirling flame, and Afrin et al. [25] investigated methane/hydrogen mixtures in MILD regime. Also ammonia blended with hydrogen has been studied with particular attention to the NO production [26]. To the authors knowledge, LES analyses carried out on pure hydrogen-air swirling flames are very limited. Mira et al. [27] investigated the injector developed at TUB addressing the capacity of flamelet combustion model to predict perfectly premixed hydrogen-air mixture under

adiabatic stable flame conditions. Nevertheless, no investigations on NO_x emissions were proposed. Only few LES works focused on NO_x estimation for gas turbine application. Meloni et al. [28] proposed LES simulation with the transport of a source term for the prediction of NO_x.

The present work aims at filling this gap by performing high-fidelity LES of a partially premixed swirling hydrogen-air flame with detailed NO_x analysis. This refers to experiments performed in the laboratory scale rig operated at TUB. To accurately predict the NO_x production, a novel Reduced Chemistry scheme for hydrogen oxidation with NO_x formation (15 species and 47 reactions) is derived and validated against detailed mechanisms and experiments. The resulting skeletal chemical scheme is then included in the compressible parallel code AVBP (<http://www.cerfacs.fr/avbp7x/>) in which turbulent combustion is handled by the dynamic formulation of the Thickened Flame LES combustion model (TFLES) [29]. To account for the effect of heat transfer on flame stabilization and NO_x formation, Conjugate Heat Transfer (CHT) simulations are performed by coupling the AVBP LES solver with the AVTP heat-conduction solver [30]. Finally, the static mesh refinement (SMR) technique is also applied to correctly resolve the flame front. The article is organized as follows: the experimental test rig is presented in section 2. The numerical methods (i.e., SMR, CHT and ARC chemistry) applied to correctly solve the turbulent hydrogen-air flame are described in section 3. Section 4 finally shows the results for both the isothermal and reactive cases with a focus on compressibility effects, air/fuel mixing, flame stabilization and NO_x formation mechanisms.

Figure 1: a) Berlin Institute of Technology experimental test rig [15]; b) numerical domain; c) grid with refinement boxes

2. Experimental Setup : TUB rig

The present numerical analysis refers to experimental measurements performed in the laboratory scale combustor developed at TUB shown in Fig. 1(a) [15]. This rig has been originally designed to study hydrogen (and syngas with high hydrogen content) swirling flames at ambient pressure. Pre-heated air at $T_{air} = 453$ K is injected through a large plenum and then is split in two separate jets: a first portion flows through an orifice (d_o) creating a central air jet whose high momentum is functional in avoiding flashback. The remaining portion enters the mixing tube through a radial swirler (Fig.1(b)). The air splitting is adjustable by changing the dimension of d_o and it is quantified by the parameter χ , defined as follows:

$$\chi = \frac{Q_{ax}}{Q_{sw} + Q_{ax}} \quad (1)$$

where Q_{ax} (m^3/s) stands for the flow rate entering the orifice and Q_{sw} , the remaining part, which flows through the swirler. Unfortunately, no detailed

measurements of χ are available. The swirl number/intensity can be controlled by moving the blocking rings highlighted in Fig.1(a)(b).

Subsonic hydrogen at $T_{fuel} = 320$ K is axially injected at 400 m/s by 16 small pipes ($d_f=0.8$ mm) circumferentially arranged at the bottom of the mixing tube (Fig.1(b)). The two air flows meet each other in the mixing tube, which is an axial pipe of length 60 mm and diameter 34 mm. In this region the flow has an average bulk velocity of 70 m/s and $Re=75000$.

Figure 2: Stable flame region

A circular combustion chamber with diameter $d_{cc}=105$ mm and length $8.8 \times d_{cc}$ is mounted at the end of the mixing tube. A large experimental campaign has been performed on this burner by varying a great variety of parameters: the orifice diameter, the air and fuel flow rates ($J = \rho_{fuel} u_{fuel}^2 / (\rho_{air} u_{air}^2)$), the fluids temperature and the swirl number (S_w). For moderate axial air injection, namely $d_o=8.0$ mm and swirl number equal to 0.9, the burner is characterized by a stable flame region represented in light blue in Fig. 2. This graph is marked off by stoichiometric conditions at the top and by the LBO condition ($\phi \approx 0.15$, dashed line) at the bottom.

In this work, two operating conditions have been investigated: first, a

cold flow point, indicated with a green star in Fig. 2, and, then, a stable flame configuration marked by the red star in the same figure. The latter is characterized by a global equivalence ratio $\phi=0.6$, which corresponds to a fuel/air momentum ratio $J=2.4$ and a thermal power output $P_{th}=105$ kW.

3. Numerical model and methods

High-fidelity LES have been performed using the AVBP code solving the compressible Navier-Stokes multi-species equations. The SIGMA subgrid-scale model is used [31] for turbulent closure. The third-order accurate Taylor-Galerkin (TGCC) scheme is used for the discretization of the convective terms with Colin et al. [32] artificial viscosity model. The turbulent flame is solved by the dynamic version of the thickened flame model (DTFLES) [29]: thickening is generally applied everywhere a reactive zone is detected by a flame sensor modelled as a function of the fuel consumption rate [33] and the thickening factor is adapted depending on the local mixture properties and grid size, to ensure sufficient resolution. Typically the thermal flame thickness (δ_T) is described with at least seven points when using semi-detailed kinetic schemes [34]. To retrieve the correct chemistry/turbulence interaction, the Charlette efficiency function has been used with a constant coefficient $\beta=0.5$ [35]. Being technically premixed flames characterised by both premix and diffusion regions [36], DTFLES has been further conditioned using the Takeno Index [37]: thickening is deactivated in diffusion flame zones, being the TFLES formalism and the efficiency functions formally applicable only to premixed flames [29]. As explained in [38], diffusion flames naturally adapt to coarse meshes and in the high Damköler regime,

their consumption speed is controlled by the turbulent fluxes.

The numerical domain is shown in Fig. 1. Few simplifications have been performed with respect to the actual rig geometry. Fuel line is simplified as 16 small pipes delivering uniformly distributed fuel mass flow. Following previous work on the same configuration [27], the 24 dilution holes presented in the original design close to the combustion chamber inlet have been also discarded to reduce the computational cost, being the total air flow rate passing through them estimated to be below 2%. For the non-reactive simulations the numerical domain is discretized with an unstructured mesh of 126 million cells with local refinement as depicted in Fig. 1. Inlet and outlet boundary conditions are treated with the Navier-Stokes Characteristic Boundary Conditions (NSCBC) [39] with a relaxation factor $k=1000 \text{ s}^{-1}$ imposed on air and fuel inlets. For the reactive case, all the walls are set no-slip and adiabatic, apart from the mixing tube walls, where the grid size used returned a $y^+ \approx 80$. For those, a wall-model (high-Reynolds approach) for imposing the wall shear stress is applied [40].

3.1. Static Mesh Refinement

Differently from cold simulations, Static Mesh Refinement (SMR) approach is employed in reactive simulations to improve flame resolutions containing computational cost. To this scope, the SMR flame criterion proposed by Agostinelli et al. [41] for CH_4 was extended to a pure hydrogen configuration. It resides on the definition of a refinement metric based on the definition of a flame probability function, i.e., a statistically relevant region of interest (ROI) in which the grid can be modified. Resolution is controlled by imposing a maximum effective thickening factor resulting from the combination of

its mean value and variance. In the present configuration, target thickening factor is set equal to 3, resulting in the 149 million cells with minimum cell dimension of $\Delta x=200 \mu\text{m}$ shown in Fig. 3. No mesh coarsening is applied in this case, since the volume already refines overlap regions of flow physics interest.

Figure 3: Comparison of the two computational grids: baseline for non reactive simulations (left), and the final grid with the SMR for reactive simulations (right).

3.2. Conjugate heat transfer

The impact of heat transfer on flame anchoring, temperature pattern and NO_x production is investigated in the present study. Conjugate heat transfer technique is applied to take into account the correct level of heat transfer from the hot gases to the solid and then towards the external ambient. This technique has been recently demonstrated to be more accurate than the heat resistance tuning at cost of increasing the computational time [36]. To this scope, the LES solver AVBP is coupled with AVTP [30, 42], a solver developed at CERFACS, which solves the thermal conduction problem. To couple the two solvers, the Parallel Coupling Strategy has been developed on the basis of CWIPI libraries [43]. A 7 million cells computational mesh has been

generated for the solid part of the burner guaranteeing at least 5 points in the wall thickness (Fig. 4). In absence of experimental measurements on the walls, a first attempt for the thermal boundary conditions on the walls has been made by evaluating the heat fluxes. The heat flux per unit of surface (W/m^2) is calculated as follows:

$$\dot{q} = U(T - T_\infty) \quad (2)$$

with the T_∞ imposed as the ambient temperature and U , the heat transfer coefficient (W/m^2K). In the most general case, the latter is evaluated as the combination of the conduction, convection and radiation heat transfer coefficients. Following the thermal-electric analogy ¹, the conduction heat transfer term is in series with an equivalent heat transfer calculated as if the convective and the radiation heat transfer terms were in parallel. Hence, U can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{1}{U} = \left(h_{cond} + \frac{1}{\frac{1}{h_{conv}} + \frac{1}{h_{rad}}} \right) \quad (3)$$

where $h_{cond} = \delta/k$ is defined as the ratio of the wall thickness (δ) over material thermal conductivity (k). The convection heat transfer coefficient, h_{conv} , is based on the Rayleigh number, an adimensional number function of the surface shape and orientation. For instance, for natural convection around a horizontal cylinder, h_{conv} can be calculated as:

$$h_{conv} = \frac{k}{D} \left(0.6 + \frac{0.387 Ra_D^{1/6}}{(1 + (0.559/Pr)^{9/16})^{8/27}} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

¹Temperature difference as the electric potential (V) and the reciprocal of the resistance ($1/R$) as the heat transfer coefficient.

The last term on the right hand side of Eq. (4) is calculated as: $h_{rad} = 1/[\sigma\epsilon(T^4 - T_\infty^4)/(T - T_\infty)]$. In this work, the conduction problem is solved by AVTP, thus on the external surfaces of the solid the heat transfer coefficient has been evaluated as the combination of the natural convection on horizontal surfaces and radiation heat transfer. The values of the heat transfer coefficients for the external combustion chamber and plenum walls are sets to 110 and 50 W/m^2K , respectively.

Figure 4: View of the boundary conditions, materials and grid of the fluid (black edges) and solid domain (red edges).

AVBP and AVTP run in parallel and exchange the solid surface temperature T_s and the heat flux q at the boundaries. The characteristic time of the fluid (τ_f) and solid (τ_s) problems are different, i.e., $\tau_s \approx 100 \tau_f$, hence the temporal coupling consists in running the LES solver for approximately 100 iterations and then running 1 iteration for the conductive problem.

3.3. Reduced scheme for H₂-air with NO_x

In the field of numerical simulations, a big challenge is to employ as accurate as possible chemical kinetic schemes. The number of species transported is usually kept low to control the computational time. For this purpose, a new reduced scheme for hydrogen-air combustion including NO_x prediction has been proposed.

Hydrogen combustion has been widely investigated since the last century in the context of oxy-fuel rocket propulsion applications. It is a light molecule with high molecular diffusivity resulting in a very low Lewis number, $Le=0.3$, if compared to classical hydrocarbons in which $Le \approx 1$ [44]. Additionally, the thermophoresis (or Soret effect) becomes relevant for hydrogen in low velocity zones in presence of temperature gradient [45]. From a modelling point of view, the kinetic species and reactions behind the combustion of hydrogen are well-known and studied, since they could be found as sub-mechanisms of all the hydrocarbon chemistries, e.g., methane and propane [46]. A large number of these detailed schemes developed for hydrocarbons and syngas could be found in literature, e.g., Gri-Mech3.0 [47], Polimi (CRECK modeling group) [48] and Galway NUIGMech1.1 [49], which have been recently integrated in the optimized C3MechV3.3 [50]. All of these well describe hydrogen/air oxidation and, also, NO_x chemistry. Despite the high precision, none of the aforementioned schemes is suitable to be directly used in a CFD code. Indeed, the computational cost of accounting for more than 30 species and thousands of reactions (some of them characterized by very small characteristic time) would make the numerical simulation unsustainable. Reduced mechanisms are required to this scope. Few examples for hydrogen-air are

the San Diego [51] and the Boivin [52] reduced mechanisms. Both are widely employed in CFD since they provide a good compromise between accuracy of the results and computational costs. Anyway, none of them includes the nitrogen oxides branches. Here a new hydrogen-air reduced mechanism is proposed, that includes the NO branches to respond to the demand of numerical computations capable of predicting the impact of H₂-air combustion in real combustion applications. Based on the experimental activity carried out on hydrogen flames, the ways to produce NO_x can be sum up in 3 categories: the thermal path defined by Zel'dovich sub-mechanism, the N₂O intermediate path and finally the secondary route through diazenyl radicals (NNH). Thermal NO_x are mainly controlled by combustion temperature since the first reaction $O + N_2 \rightleftharpoons NO + N$ involves elevated energy of activation. The N₂O intermediate chemistry is, on the contrary, low sensitive to temperature because it is led by a third body reaction which necessitates low energy of activation [9]. Moreover, the N₂O route is promoted at low temperature, lean condition and high pressure. Finally, the NNH route is promoted in the flame front and controlled by the radicals O and H. Besides, it is activated at all the temperatures with short residence time. Another important aspect to underline is the link between NNH and N₂O:

The reduced mechanism was obtained with the ARCANE code co-developed by CERFACS and Cornell University [53]. It is a fully automatic multi-step reduction tool relying on DRGEP [54], chemical lumping [55] and Quasi-Steady State Assumption [56]. CRECK detailed mechanism [48], which comprises 159 species and 2459 reactions was chosen as a reference for this work

because of its extensive use in the community. An error of 5% is set as a limit for the ignition time delay as well as for the laminar flame speed, whereas, a maximum error of 1% has been imposed on the integral value of NO. The reduction process, which targets chains for the production of NO via N_2O and NNH secondary routes, returns a skeletal scheme with 15 species and only 47 reactions. The set of species and reactions can be consulted in the Supplementary Material. It is important to highlight that in the reduction process, the O and H radicals have been set as main targets being central for the O_2/H_2 and NO oxidation pathways.

Cantera predictions (www.cantera.org) of laminar flame speed of an unstained premixed flame on a wide range of pressures and temperatures conditions are shown in Fig. 5(a-b-c). The calculations have been carried out by activating the detailed transport (multi-species) method and the Soret effect. Results with the reduced scheme are compared to the detailed CRECK and the skeletal scheme of Boivin et al. [52] as a benchmark. A good agreement is observed between the detailed and the reduced schemes, whereas some discrepancies can be observed with the existing skeletal scheme without NOx [52] especially at pressures far from the atmospheric pressure (Fig. 5(a)) and high temperatures (Fig. 5(c)).

Figure 5: Comparison of laminar flames speed calculated with detailed transport (multi-species) for detailed (blue circles) [48], skeletal (black) [52] and reduced scheme (red) at elevated pressure (a), low pressure (b) and elevated temperatures (c).

Finally the reduced scheme has been validated on experiments performed on laminar diffusion flames ($Re=400$) diluted with inert at constant strain rate $a=100$ s^{-1} [8]. Two counterflow flames with a global equivalence ratio of $\phi = 0.9$ & 1.4 , and same strain rate as in the experiments, were computed in Cantera. In Fig. 6(a) the lean case has been calculated also with the Gri-Mech 3.0 and 2.11 [47, 57], and the Galway schemes. The two Gri-Mech mechanisms over-predict the width and the peak of the NO profile, which instead is well captured by CRECK and the reduced schemes, herein proposed. The Galway resolves accurately the maximum value, but shows a second ripple which is not evidenced by experiments. Furthermore, when the Soret effect is activated in the rich case (Fig. 6(b)) a slight over-prediction of the NO concentration is noted. This effect is present in both detailed and reduced mechanisms, thus it does not directly depend on the reduction procedure. Nevertheless, the proposed scheme correctly reproduces NO experimental profiles [8].

Figure 6: NO profiles (a-b) calculated for counterflow flames and compared with experimental data [8] at $p = 1$ bar, $T = 300$ K and fixed strain $a = 100$ s^{-1} .

Once validated, NO formation routes can be investigated using this skeletal mechanism for the global operating condition investigated in this study, $\phi = 0.6$. A 1D premixed unstrained flame has been calculated in Cantera and its reaction paths are shown in Fig. 6. This graph shows the fluxes of the element according to their net reaction rates. The number associated to the single path are the reaction rates normalized to the highest value in the graph. Moreover, for each path, the species involved in the reactions are noted.

Figure 7: The reaction paths for an hydrogen flame at $T_{ad} \approx 1850$ K using the skeletal mechanism, where the arrow thickness stands for normalized fluxes of the reaction rate (where 1 is the maximum).

Looking at Fig. 7, it is noted that thermal and N₂O paths represent the first steps of oxidation immediately followed by second routes NNH, in accordance with Skottenne et al. [9]. The diagram shows, NNH pathway mainly produces N₂O as expected by Eq.(5). The reduction process was therefore able to preserve important reactions for the final NO production, refer to supplementary material, as well as the link between the secondary routes which, on the contrary, are absent in the Gri-Mech mechanisms.

To give an idea of the impact of hydrogen combustion on the production of the powerful GHG N₂O, two 1D premixed laminar unstretched flames have been calculated at constant burnt gases temperature (T=1840 K) using the aforementioned detailed kinetic scheme [48]. A comparison has been carried out between CH₄-air and H₂-air reactant mixtures. Global equivalence ratio of $\phi \approx 0.6$ and 0.7 have been considered, respectively for hydrogen

and methane, to keep constant burnt gas temperature. The results show a value of N_2O mass fraction for hydrogen combustion doubled compared to methane combustion. Although this is a simplified calculation, it shows what is implied by the widespread use of hydrogen for future aviation and power generation. Eventually, the reduced scheme proposed by the authors take into account some important reactions that link NO_x to N_2O oxidation, namely:

thus providing also a reliable evaluation of N_2O species for H_2 -air combustion.

When used in AVBP, the reduced skeletal scheme is coupled with simplified constant $Le \neq 1$ transport properties, consisting in determining the viscosity from a power law and deducing the mixture heat conductivity using a constant Prandtl (Pr) number while each species diffusivity relies on a constant Schmidt (Sc) number. This approach often present in LES codes allows to account for differential diffusion between different species. Pr and Sc numbers for each transported species of the mechanism have been optimised in order to fit multicomponent transport and Soret effect. Values are reported in the supplementary materials.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Cold flow analysis and validation

Figure 8: Cold flow - a) Axial velocity (u_z) profiles at different streamwise positions inside the combustion chamber and b) relative contours [58, 27].

Figure 9: Cold flow - a) Radial velocity (u_r) profiles at different streamwise positions inside the combustion chamber and b) relative contours [58, 27].

As in the experiments, no fuel is considered in the cold flow LES. Time-averaged and root mean square (RMS) profiles of the axial and radial velocity components extracted from an averaged solution (50 *ms* after initial transition died out) at different locations along the stream-wise direction (5.4, 11.3, 31.0 and 60.5 *mm*) are compared with experimental PIV data in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, respectively. The numerical velocity profiles show a good agreement with experiments with some discrepancies in the central part of the recirculation zone close to the backplane (5.4 *mm*). This can be due to the experimental uncertainties, since measurements of flow velocity components in the proximity of the backplane are a great challenge due to PIV laser reflection to the walls. The profiles and the levels of RMS are also comparable with experiments. Experimental tangential profiles have not been collected during the experiments, therefore the numerical results have not been reported. Finally, the velocity contours indicate that the structure of the recirculation zones and its opening flow angle are in accordance with the experiments.

Figure 10: a) Mach number comparison between two different grid refinements; b) density contours comparison between two different grid refinements.

Being the cold flow simulation analysed, the air jet flowing through the axial orifice is now investigated. Looking at the instantaneous contours of the Mach number in orifice zone, Fig. 10(a), one can see that the flow is slightly below the transonic regime (mean Mach = 0.55), pointing out the importance of solving this case with a compressible solver in contrast with the cases already presented in literature. Compressibility effects can be also discussed by observing the flow density in the orifice region: a density reduction of about 22% is achieved inside the axial passage, Fig. 10(b). Unfortunately, no experimental data are available for a comparison with the actual pressure drop. For this reason, as described in section 3, mesh refinement has been performed in this volume aiming at accurately solving the jet dynamics, the pressure drop, and in return, the air flow splitting rate. In Fig. 10, the field of Mach number is compared for two different grid resolutions. The grid on the left (a coarse mesh with 44 M cells) has been generated with a minimum

cell size in the axial duct and mixing tube of $400 \mu m$. On the right is the final grid used for the calculation with a refinement up to $250 \mu m$. A grid independence study has been carried out by refining progressively the grid until no substantial variation of the pressure level downstream of the orifice could be recorded. To give an idea of the pressure levels in this region, the pressure has been recorded inside the plenum, at the exit of the orifice and close to the swirler outlet. The average pressure at the exit of the orifice is around $89 kPa$ with no remarkable pressure oscillations. Thus, the pressure drop through the orifice (Δp) is of the order of $23 kPa$.

The grid size demonstrates to affect the structure of the jet, its length and wrinkling; this also impacts the equivalence ratio distribution in the mixing tube for the successive hot flow results. Moreover, looking at the outer radius of the mixing tube, also the flow resolution in this region is clearly improved when the minimum grid size is reduced. For the selected operating conditions and diameter of the orifice, the value of air splitting χ obtained by LES without fuel injection (cold case) with Eq. (5) indicates that 14.2% of the flow rate flows through the orifice. The axial flow could change from cold to hot case since the injection of fuel introduces a local pressure reduction and consequently a larger flow rate enters the swirler ($\chi=13\%$). Unfortunately, it is not possible to compare these values with experiments, but they are in line with the previous calculation reported by Tanneberger et al. [59].

4.2. Reactive case: mixing process, stable flame analysis and pollutants prediction

After assessing the cold flow simulation, the stable reactive case at global equivalence ratio $\phi = 0.6$ is investigated. As a first step, an analysis of the mixing process is performed to evaluate the spatial mixture distribution before entering the combustion chamber. Eventually, being hydrogen a molecule characterized by peculiar properties, a specific analysis is dedicated to the study of the flame structure and then to the NOx formation.

4.2.1. Mixing process

Figure 11: Instantaneous field of equivalence ratio in a longitudinal section and in two sections normal to the axial direction.

In Fig. 11, an instantaneous plot of equivalence ratio in a longitudinal plane points out the dynamics of the mixing process. The air coming from the swirler (bent white arrows) pushes the fuel coming from the small pipes

towards the conical surface. The conical surface borders an axial pipe rim connected to the orifice. In this zone, the mixture is extremely rich. After that, the mixture enters the mixing tube and decelerates. In the first part of the mixing tube, the mixing process is governed by the combination of both the swirling flow and axial jet. A blue gap in the axial region highlights the spatial influence of the axial air jet. An annulus of confined rich mixture is visible on a section at the bottom of the mixing tube (Fig. 11). By the half of the tube, the turbulent vortical structures enhance the mixing and the contours exhibit a more homogeneous ϕ distribution.

Figure 12: a) Mean field of the equivalence ratio; b) equivalence ratio ϕ and mixture fraction z profiles along the radial direction inside the tube at different axial locations.

Mean equivalence ratio field is shown in Fig. 12 with iso-contours of the global equivalence ratio $\phi=0.6$. The mixture close to the walls appears leaner

than the global equivalence ratio. The plot on the right illustrates the mixture fraction z (and equivalence ratio ϕ) along the radial direction inside the tube at -60 and -0.1 mm upstream the combustion chamber inlet. The target value is represented by a blue dash dot line. In the first part of the mixing tube, the mixture fraction close to the walls is dominated by the swirled air flow; the z deficit in the central part is due to the axial jet penetration confirming the importance of grid refinement in this zone, Fig. 10. At the end of the mixing zone, the mixture is still lean at outer radii, while it remains slightly rich in the central part. Before entering the combustion chamber, mixture is not perfectly premixed being the variability of the equivalence ratio in the range $\pm 10\%$ around the global value. This confirms the necessity to take air/fuel injection and the mixing process into account in the numerical model. It is remarkable that even at the first stages of the mixing process, the level of the local equivalence ratio is higher than the lower limit of hydrogen flammability ($\phi=0.1$). It can also be said that the length of the mixing tube has a remarkable impact on the mixture composition at the entrance of the combustion chamber. This results are in line with the experiments performed on the same burner in a water tunnel [15].

4.2.2. Stable flame and impact of the conjugate heat transfer

Previous works on this configuration have been performed by solving the case under adiabatic condition [27]. Thus, in what follows, the importance of taking into account the thermal boundary conditions via LES-CHT simulations is assessed by comparing adiabatic and non-adiabatic flames.

Figure 13: Averaged contours from LES of OH (top left), in adiabatic condition (left half) and with CHT (right half), compared with experimental OH signal probability (top right). Bottom: zoom on the anchoring zone in the LES with adiabatic condition (left half) and with CHT (right half) [58]

In Fig. 13 the averaged OH fields from adiabatic and LES-CHT cases are compared to mean OH signal probability measures [58]. The OH radical delimits the reaction zone with a good accuracy. A M-shape flame is observed in agreement with experiments [58]. Interestingly, the application of the CHT modifies the quantity of OH mass fraction produced improving the agreement with experimental observations: when heat losses are applied the anchoring branches are indeed less intense and detached from the backplane rim (see Fig. 13 bottom). However in both LES, the iso-line of OH mass fraction points out that the central part of the flame is lifted from the backplane, while the experiments show a high probability to find OH close to the combustion

chamber entrance.

Figure 14: Instantaneous fields of a) Takeno Index conditioned by the HRR; b) thickening factor.

In Fig. 14(a), an instantaneous plot of the heat release rate (HRR) of LES-CHT colored by the Takeno Index (T_I) is shown. The contours reveal a value of $T_I=1$ in the flame front, thus indicating that the combustion process happens in mainly premixed condition. Nevertheless, diffusion spots are visible in the post flame region. Thickening is correctly not applied in those flame regions as confirmed in Fig. 14(b). In Fig. 14(b), the value of thickening factor varies in a range from 1 to 5. In the part of the flame region, it can be observed a value $F=3$, which is the target value applied during the SMR.

Figure 15: Velocity profiles of the hot case and contours of the axial velocity [58, 27].

The velocity profiles of adiabatic and the LES-CHT cases are compared with PIV data at different locations along the streamwise direction (5.4, 9.4, 21.2 and 40.9 mm) in Fig. 15. The velocity profiles for CHT cases are slightly in better accordance with the experiments. In both cases a little deficit of the axial velocity is observed in the central recirculation zone, which may be related to the more slightly upstream position of the central flame in the LES, as already seen above. The level of RMS for the axial velocity is comparable between experiments and numerical simulations.

Figure 16: (a) Comparison of temperature [K] field with two iso-curves of temperature, one at the adiabatic flame temperature ($T_{ad} = 1850 K$ at $\phi=0.6$) and the second at $1750 K$. Four iso-curves of temperature in the solid part. (b) Temperature contours of the solid part with an iso-contours of HRR colored by temperature.

To further investigate the impact of the CHT on the flame stabilization and pollutant emissions, a comparison of temperature, heat release rate, NO and N_2O is done for both the adiabatic and LES-CHT cases. As expected, in Fig. 16, the temperature field puts in evidence the heat losses at the walls. CHT approach gives access to information on the thermal pattern in the solid, illustrated with iso-contours of $T=700, 650, 600$ and $550 K$ drawn on a slice of the solid domain. A 3D longitudinal cut of the solid part coloured by temperature shows the overall variability of the temperature in the solid (Fig. 16(b)). The combustion chamber which contains hot gases is responsible for the major part of heat losses and heats the walls up to a temperature around $1200K$. Part of this heat diffuses to the backplane leading there to a non uniform temperature radial distribution between $700K$ (close to the chamber corner) to $550K$. As this temperature is higher than the flow

temperature in the final part of the mixing tube (a value close to the pre-heated air temperature, $453K$), the solid heats back the flow in this zone. An estimation of the heat transferred through the various solid parts is reported in Tab. 1: a large amount of heat is transferred from the combustion chamber to the ambient, due to the presence of hot gases; the backplane is heated by both the hot gases in the combustion chamber and by conduction from the chamber walls; finally heat is redistributed in the plenum volume and back to the flow around the mixing tube. The external plenum walls diffuse heat to the external ambient as well, for details refer to section 3.2.

	Combustion chamber	Backplane	Mixing tube
heat transfer [kW]	-14.0	-1.3	0.4

Table 1: Heat transferred through the solid parts: combustion chamber, backplane and mixing tube.

Figure 17: Comparison of the averaged HRR [W/m^3] and NO mass fraction between the adiabatic and non-adiabatic cases.

The mean heat release rate distributions (Fig. 17) slightly differ between the adiabatic and non-adiabatic cases, confirming what was already observed

from the OH mass fraction field (Fig. 13). Indeed, the adiabatic flame has a high heat release rate close to the backplane, where typically the M-flame is anchored. This is a direct result of the higher flow temperature in the external recirculation zone, which enhances the reactivity of fresh mixture coming from the mixing tube. A consequence is a slightly narrower central zone of heat release rate in the adiabatic case, as evidenced by the iso-contour at 10^8 (W/m^3).

In terms of NO produced by the two models, one can see in Fig. 17 that the higher temperature of the adiabatic case leads to higher value of NO mass fraction, in particular in the central recirculation zone where it is also more uniform. This is highlighted by an isoline at $Y_{NO}=1.2e^{-6}$. When heat losses are considered, the NO globally decreases and its peak production remains in a limited region close to the inner shear layer zone. To give an idea of the amount of NOx produced by this burner, two different parameters have been evaluated for the LES-CHT case. The NOx emission index defined as the mass (in g) of pollutant divided by the mass (in kg) of fuel burned, results here to $0.77 gNOx/kg_{fuel}$, and the concentration of NOx in part per million volume at the gas turbine standard, which is equal to 7 ppmv at 15%O2 dry. This value is in line with the experiments (7-8.5 ppmv, Fig. 15 in Ref.[58]) confirming the effectiveness of the reduced kinetic model in predicting the right level of emission in a real combustor.

Figure 18: Comparison of the N_2O mass fraction on a longitudinal plane and on a section towards the end of the combustion chamber between the adiabatic and non-adiabatic cases.

As discussed in the introduction, an estimation of the amount of N_2O produced during the operation of this burner can be helpful for the future technology development related to hydrogen combustion. The averaged N_2O field is compared between the two cases on a slice in Fig. 18. It is remarkable that the N_2O mass fraction increases close to the walls for the non-adiabatic flame (LES-CHT), as a consequence of the local lower temperature due to heat losses. Looking at a transverse section normal to the burner axis close to the exit of the combustion chamber, a ring of increased N_2O mass fraction can be seen close to the wall where the temperature is reduced in the non-adiabatic case. The exact chemical process will be detailed in the next

section, but few considerations can be done here. The reactions that lead to N_2O formation are easily activated. After that, the abundance of N_2O is converted into NO due to the high temperature ($>1800 K$). Indeed, comparing Figs. 16 and 18, it can be observed that the regions where temperature is lower than $1800 K$ are the ones where N_2O has not been oxidized. For the case studied in this work with the application of the conjugate heat transfer, the N_2O emission index is $0.06 gN_2O/kg_{fuel}$ and compared to the adiabatic one, it produces +40% of N_2O mass fraction at the exit of the burner.

4.2.3. Differential diffusion effect and analysis of pollutant production

Figure 19: Instantaneous fields of HRR and ϕ in a vertical cut plane for the LES+CHT case, with an isocontour of HRR at $2 \times 10^9 (W/m^3)$. Representation of the concave and convex parts around the flame front.

It is worth to investigate the behaviour of the hydrogen molecules in proximity of the reaction zone which is outlined in Fig. 19 by an iso-contour of heat release rate equal to $2 \times 10^9 (W/m^3)$. A wrinkled surface is observed

as expected in regime of turbulent combustion. Due to differential diffusion effects, convex curvatures are prone to accumulate light molecules, such as H_2 and the radical H , whereas, concave surfaces are adjacent to lean mixture spots. This is confirmed by the equivalence ratio contours showing a great variability in this region.

Figure 20: Instantaneous fields of O, H, NO mass fractions and temperature in a vertical cut plane close to the chamber inlet for the LES+CHT case, with an isocontour of HRR at 2×10^9 (W/m^3).

As discussed in section 3.3, the NO production in hydrogen combustion involves three different routes: thermal NO, N_2O and NNH. In Fig. 21, a schematic representation provides an easy representation of the reactions, molecules and atoms involved in this process. This sketch does not want to be exhaustive of all the species and reaction that play a role in the NO production, but it helps the reader to focus on the chemical processes discussed thereafter.

Figure 21: Schematic representation of the pathways, reactions and molecules involved in the NO formation for H_2 combustion.

Figure 20(a) reports an instantaneous field of radical O close to the chamber inlet. It can be seen that it is present not only in the post flame region, but peaks are already visible in the reacting zone. This contributes to the thermal NO production, and is in line with the conclusions presented by Homer et al. [6]. The radical O is not affected by fast diffusion, but it favours the low activation energy reaction producing N_2O and successively its oxidation into NO, Fig. 21. The same can be said for the light radical H (Fig. 20(b)), formed in the reacting zone. However, since H is a really light atom, it is affected by fast diffusion and peaks in convex-shaped flame zones. H atoms give their contribution to the heat release rate through reactions 4 and 20 of the reaction list given in the Supplementary Materials. It comes

into play in various oxidation processes in the NNH route, for instance the fixation of molecular nitrogen to NNH as indicated in Fig. 21. The contours of NO and temperature (Fig. 20(c-d), respectively) show a good correlation in the peak zones. In the other regions at lower temperature, the secondary routes contribute to the fixation of molecular nitrogen. It is also important to highlight the slowest time of the NO chemistry. Indeed, the NO starts appearing in the post flame zone.

Figure 22: For the LES+CHT case: a) Iso-surface of $c=0.9$ colored by temperature; b) scatter plot of the temperature as function of the mixture fraction on the iso- $c=0.9$.

To deepen the NO_x dynamics, scatter plots on instantaneous iso-progress variable (c) surfaces are hereafter discussed. The progress variable is defined as a normalized function of the product H₂O mass fraction. Temperature is firstly investigated in Fig. 22 on a progress variable surface at $c=0.9$. On the right, the scatter plot of the temperature as function of the mixture fraction on the same surface colored by a probability density function (PDF) evidences the proximity of all the points to the target value represented by a vertical line. The mixture fraction used in the code is the one defined by

Bilger [60]:

$$z = \frac{\beta - \beta_{ox}}{\beta_{fuel} - \beta_{ox}} \quad (8)$$

where *ox* and *fuel* stand for oxidizer and fuel, respectively. In Eq. 8, $\beta = 2Y_C/W_C + 0.5Y_H/W_H - Y_O/W_O$, with Y_i the atomic mass fraction and W_i its molecular weight.

Two clouds of point can be detected, one around higher temperature (adiabatic flame temperature of hydrogen at $\phi=0.6$) and one around lower temperature (≈ 1000 K). The latter cloud of points refers to the region close to the backplane, where the reduction of temperature is caused by the heat losses.

Figure 23: LES+CHT: scatter plots of NO, N_2O and NNH as functions of temperature on different iso- c surfaces: 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9. The red line corresponds to 1D flame at the same temperature and equivalence ratio.

In order to investigate the effectiveness of the reduced kinetic model used in the present lean hydrogen turbulent flame, several scatter plots of the main species involved in the NO production are proposed. The reader is invited to refer to Fig. 21 to follow this analysis. In Fig. 23(a), the mass fraction of NO has been plotted on 4 different iso- c surfaces at 0.3, 0.5, 0.7 and 0.9. The NO mass fraction obtained by a 1D premixed flame calculation with Cantera (www.cantera.org), employing the detailed kinetic scheme at

the same temperature and equivalence ratio is superimposed. Overall the 3D LES results are in line with the 1D cases, and exhibit important turbulent dispersion. As expected, thermal NO pathway is predominant given the final temperature above 1800 K .

In Fig. 23(b-c), the same plots have been made for the N_2O and NNH precursors. As it has been observed for NO, the behavior of these species follow the trend predicted by the 1D flame. Moreover, it can be noticed how both N_2O and NNH start growing at $T=800 K$ due to the fixation of N_2 with atomic oxygen and atomic hydrogen. Furthermore, the steep decrease of NNH radical and the fast growth of N_2O suggest that there is a link between these two molecules. This is also evidenced by experiments and analytical models found in the literature [9]. To highlight the associated chemical reaction, mentioned in section 3.3, the scatter plot in Fig. 24 has been added. The hyperbolic trend of this plot means that when NNH is lowest, it has been converted into N_2O through the reaction described in Eq. (5) and vice-versa. Finally, one can say that the NNH path does not only directly contribute to the formation of NO, but it enhances the formation of N_2O then converted into NO by reactions with H and O also in the post flame region, as already shown in Fig. 20 in Section 4.2.3. Only the remaining part of NNH participates directly to the NO production thanks to the thicken layer of O radical, see Figs. 20 21.

Figure 24: LES+CHT: (left) scatter plots of NNH and N_2O mass fractions on different iso- c surfaces: 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9., the red line corresponds to 1D flame at the same temperature and equivalence ratio; (right) scatter plot of NNH and H mass fractions on an iso- $c=0.7$ isosurface at $c=0.7$ (right) colored by a probability density function.

The production of NNH and its successive oxidation into NO is directly linked to the presence of radicals H and O. This is pointed out by the scatter plot colored by a probability density function, which correlates the NNH and the H species on an iso- $c=0.7$ isosurface (Fig. 24(b)). H is a light molecule that gather by fast diffusion in convex regions of the wrinkled flame. This means that in those regions the NOx production is not only favored by the high H_2 mass fraction, and consequently by the high temperature, but also by the presence of radicals which enhances the NO oxidation.

In the end, LES model with the reduced kinetic model proposed in this work proves to be a reliable tool for the prediction of NOx produced by a H_2 -air turbulent flame. Even if only global NOx data are available on the experimental burner, and no local information can be used for the validation, the good agreement between the LES results and the canonical 1D flames calculated with the detailed kinetic scheme, allows to be confident for further

study on premixed and diffusion turbulent flames.

5. Conclusions

The swirled stabilized burner developed at TUB for the combustion of hydrogen-air has been investigated by means of high fidelity compressible LES simulations. To this scope, a new reduced mechanism has been developed with ARCANE starting from the detailed scheme proposed by the CRECK modeling group. The reduced skeletal scheme is characterized by 15 species and 47 reactions and has been validated against premixed and diffusion flames available in the literature. Cold flow simulations have been performed paying attention to the axial air jet, designed to contrast flashback, and to the mixing process. Indeed, simulations show that the flow developed inside the orifice is slightly below the transonic regime, thus compressibility effects need to be considered to recover the right mixture formation. Furthermore, a reactive stable case has been investigated ($\phi=0.6$). The typical M-flame shape flame has been validated. Both HRR and OH fields have been qualitatively compared with experiments. A comparison of the adiabatic and LES-CHT flames has been proposed. This shows the importance to consider the appropriate level of heat boundary losses in order to capture the right level of temperature in the central and external recirculation zones and consequently the right level of NOx. In order to study the impact of hydrogen on the flame structure, an analysis has been carried out on the flame front. Convex and concave sections have been detected, pointing out the effect of the preferential diffusion. Finally, the analysis of the NOx formation confirmed the presence of two pathways for the generation of NOx, one governed

by N_2O and one by NNH. In the end the numerical set and the new reduced scheme demonstrate to be able to capture the right level of NO_x produced by a pure hydrogen flame.

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